

FEKETE-SZEGO INEQUALITIES AND (j, k) -SYMMETRIC FUNCTIONS
USING q -DERIVATIVE

C. Selvaraj*, S. Varadharajan** & S. Lakshmi***

* Department of Mathematics, Presidency College (Autonomous), Chennai, Tamilnadu

** Mathematics Section, Department of Information Technology, Al Musanna College of Technology,
Muscat, Sultanate of Oman

*** Department of Mathematics, R.M.K.Engineering College, R.S.M.Nagar, Kavaraipettai, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: C. Selvaraj, S. Varadharajan & S. Lakshmi, "Fekete-Szego Inequalities and (j, k) -Symmetric Functions Using q -Derivative", International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education, Special Issue, July, Page Number 136-147, 2017.

Abstract:

In this paper sharp upper bounds of $|a_3 - \mu a_2^2|$ for functions belonging to new subclasses defined using the concept of (j, k) -symmetric functions using q -derivative are derived. Furthermore, the application of the results are also illustrated.

Key Words: Analytic Function; Univalent Function; Schwarz Function; q -Starlike, q -Convex, q -Derivative Operator, Subordination & Fekete-Szegő Inequality.

1. Introduction:

The q -difference calculus or quantum calculus was initiated at the beginning of 19th century that was initially developed by Jackson [16, 15]. Basic definitions and properties of q -difference calculus can be found in the book mentioned in [17]. The fractional q -difference calculus had its origin in the works by Al-Salam [3] and Agarwal [1]. Recently, the area of q -calculus has attracted the serious attention of researchers. The great interest is due to its application in various branches of mathematics and physics. Mohammed and Darus [21] studied approximation and geometric properties of these q -operators for some subclasses of analytic functions in compact disk.

Let $\mathbf{A}$ denote the class of all analytic function of the form

$$f(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n z^n, \quad (1.1)$$

in the open unit disc $\mathbf{U} = \{z : z \in \mathbf{C}; |z| < 1\}$. Let $\mathbf{S}$ be the subclass of $\mathbf{A}$ consisting of functions which are univalent in $\mathbf{U}$.

If f and g are analytic in $\mathbf{U}$, we say that the function f is subordinate to g , written as $f(z) \prec g(z)$ in $\mathbf{U}$, if there exist a Schwarz function $w(z)$, which is analytic in $\mathbf{U}$ with $w(0) = 0$ and $|w(z)| < 1$ such that $f(z) = g(w(z))$ for $z \in \mathbf{U}$. Furthermore, if the function $g(z)$ is univalent in $\mathbf{U}$, then we have the following equivalence holds (see [9] and [20]):

$$f(z) \prec g(z) \Leftrightarrow f(0) = g(0) \quad \text{and} \quad f(\mathbf{U}) \subset g(\mathbf{U}).$$

For function $f \in \mathbf{A}$ given by (1.1) and $0 < q < 1$, the q -derivative of a function f is defined by (see [15, 16])

$$D_q f(z) = \frac{f(z) - f(qz)}{(1-q)z} \quad (z \neq 0), \quad (1.2)$$

$D_q f(0) = f'(0)$ and $D_q^2 f(z) = D_q(D_q f(z))$. From (1.2), we deduce that

$$D_q f(z) = 1 + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} [n]_q a_n z^{n-1}, \quad (1.3)$$

where

$$[n]_q = \frac{1 - q^n}{1 - q}. \quad (1.4)$$

As $q \rightarrow 1^-$, $[n]_q \rightarrow n$. For a function $h(z) = z^n$, we observe that

$$D_q(h(z)) = D_q(z^n) = \frac{1 - q^n}{1 - q} z^{n-1} = [n]_q z^{n-1},$$

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} D_q(h(z)) = \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} ([n]_q z^{n-1}) = n z^{n-1} = h'(z),$$

where h' is the ordinary derivative.

As a right inverse, Jackson [15] introduced the q -integral

$$\int_0^z h(t) d_q t = z(1-q) \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^n f(zq^n),$$

provided that the series converges. For a function $h(z) = z^n$, we observe that

$$\int_0^z h(t) d_q t = \lim_{q \rightarrow 1^-} \frac{z^{n+1}}{[n+1]_q} = \frac{z^{n+1}}{n+1} = \int_0^z h(t) dt,$$

where $\int_0^z h(t) dt$ is the ordinary integral.

Ma and Minda [19] unified various subclasses of starlike and convex functions for which either quantity $zf'(z)/f(z)$ or quantity $1 + zf''(z)/f'(z)$ is subordinate to a more general superordinate function. For this purpose, they considered an analytic function ϕ with positive real part in the unit disc $\mathbf{U}$, with $\phi(0) = 1$, $\phi'(0) > 0$, and ϕ maps $\mathbf{U}$ onto a region starlike, with respect to the real axis.

The class of Ma-Minda starlike functions $f(z) \in \mathbf{A}$ consists of functions satisfying the subordination $zf'(z)/f(z) \prec \phi(z)$. Similarly, the class of Ma-Minda convex functions consists of functions $f(z) \in \mathbf{A}$ satisfying the subordination $1 + zf''(z)/f'(z) \prec \phi(z)$.

Let k be a positive integer and $\varepsilon = \exp(2\pi i/k)$. A domain $\mathbf{D}$ is said to be k -fold symmetric if a rotation of $\mathbf{D}$ about the origin through an angle $2\pi/k$ carries $\mathbf{D}$ onto itself. A function $f \in \mathbf{A}$ is said to be k -fold symmetric in $\mathbf{U}$ if for each $z \in \mathbf{U}$

$$f(\varepsilon z) = \varepsilon f(z).$$

The family of all k -fold symmetric functions is denoted by $\mathbf{S}^k$ and for $k = 2$, we get class of the odd univalent functions. The notion of (j, k) -symmetric functions ($k = 2, 3, \dots; j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, (k-1)$) is a generalization of even, odd, k -symmetrical functions. Let $\varepsilon = \exp(2\pi i/k)$ and $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, (k-1)$ where $k \geq 2$ is a natural number. A function $f: \mathbf{U} \rightarrow \mathbf{C}$ is called (j, k) -symmetrical if

$$f(\varepsilon^j z) = \varepsilon^j f(z), \quad z \in \mathbf{U}.$$

We note that the family of all (j, k) -symmetric functions is denoted by $\mathbf{S}^{(j,k)}$. Also, $\mathbf{S}^{(0,2)}$, $\mathbf{S}^{(1,2)}$ and $\mathbf{S}^{(1k)}$ are called even, odd and k -symmetric functions respectively.

We have the following decomposition theorem (see [18]).

For every mapping $f: \mathbf{D} \rightarrow \mathbf{C}$, and $\mathbf{D}$ is a k -fold symmetric set, there exist exactly the sequence of (j, k) -symmetrical functions $f_{j,k}$,

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} f_{j,k}(z), \quad (1.5)$$

where

$$f_{j,k}(z) = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{v=0}^{k-1} \varepsilon^{-vj} f(\varepsilon^v z), \quad (1.6)$$

$$(f \in \mathbf{A}; k = 1, 2, \dots; j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, (k-1)).$$

The decomposition (1.5) is a generalization of the well-known fact that each function defined on a symmetrical subset $\mathbf{U}$ of $\mathbf{C}$ can be uniquely represented as the sum of an even function and an odd function (see Theorem 1 of [18]). From (1.6), we can get

$$f_{j,k}(z) = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{v=0}^{k-1} \varepsilon^{-vj} f(\varepsilon^v z) = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{v=0}^{k-1} \varepsilon^{-vj} \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n (\varepsilon^v z)^n \right),$$

then

$$f_{j,k}(z) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \psi_n a_n z^n, \quad a_1 = 1, \quad \psi_n = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{v=0}^{k-1} \varepsilon^{(n-j)v} = \begin{cases} 1 & n = lk + j; \\ 0 & n \neq lk + j. \end{cases} \quad (1.7)$$

Definition 1.1 (see [4]) Let $\phi(z) = 1 + B_1 z + B_2 z^2 + B_3 z^3 + \dots$ be univalent starlike with respect to 1 which maps the unit disk $\mathbf{U}$ onto a region in the right half plane which is symmetric with respect to the real axis. Let $0 \leq \beta \leq \alpha \leq 1$ and $B_1 > 0$. Then the function $f(z) \in \mathbf{A}$ is in the class $\mathbf{S}_{j,k}(\phi)$ if

$$\frac{zf'(z)}{f_{j,k}(z)} \prec \phi(z).$$

Definition 1.2 A function $f \in \mathbf{A}$ is said to be in the class $\mathbf{S}_{j,k}^q(\phi)$ if it satisfies the following subordination condition:

$$\frac{zD_q f(z)}{f_{j,k}(z)} \prec \phi(z) \quad (\phi \in \mathbf{P}). \quad (1.8)$$

Definition 1.3 A function $f \in \mathbf{A}$ is said to be in the class $\mathbf{C}_{j,k}^q(\phi)$, if it satisfies the following subordination condition:

$$\frac{D_q(zD_q f(z))}{D_q f_{j,k}(z)} \prec \phi(z) \quad (\phi \in \mathbf{P}). \quad (1.9)$$

Lemma 1 [19] Let $p(z) \in \mathbf{P}$ and also let v be a complex number, then

$$|c_2 - v c_1^2| \leq 2 \max\{1, |2v - 1|\},$$

the result is sharp for functions given by

$$p(z) = \frac{1+z^2}{1-z^2}, \quad p(z) = \frac{1+z}{1-z}.$$

Lemma 2 [19] Let $p(z) \in \mathbf{P}$, then

$$|c_2 - v c_1^2| \leq \begin{cases} -4v + 2, & \text{if } v \leq 0; \\ 2, & \text{if } 0 \leq v \leq 1; \\ 4v - 2, & \text{if } v \geq 1. \end{cases} \quad (1.10)$$

When $v < 0$ or $v > 1$, the equality holds if and only if $p(z) = (1+z)/(1-z)$ or one of its rotations. If $0 < v < 1$, then the equality if and only if $p(z) = (1+z^2)/(1-z^2)$ or one of its rotations. If $v = 0$, the equality holds if and only if

$$p(z) = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\varrho\right) \frac{1+z}{1-z} + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}\varrho\right) \frac{1-z}{1+z}, \quad (0 \leq \varrho \leq 1),$$

or one of its rotations. If $v = 1$, the equality holds if and only if

$$\frac{1}{p(z)} = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\varrho\right) \frac{1+z}{1-z} + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}\varrho\right) \frac{1-z}{1+z}, \quad (0 \leq \varrho \leq 1).$$

Also the above upper bound is sharp and it can be improved as follows when $0 \leq v \leq 1$

$$\begin{aligned} |c_2 - v c_1^2| + v |c_1|^2 &\leq 2, & (0 < v \leq 1/2), \\ |c_2 - v c_1^2| + (1-v) |c_1|^2 &\leq 2, & (1/2 \leq v < 1). \end{aligned}$$

In the present paper, we obtain the Fekete-Szegő inequalities for the class $\mathbf{S}_{j,k}^q(\phi)$ and $\mathbf{C}_{j,k}^q(\phi)$. We employ the technique adapted by Ma and Minda [19] to find the coefficient estimates for our class.

2. Main Results:

Unless otherwise mentioned, we assume throughout this paper that the function $0 < q < 1, \phi \in \mathbf{P}, [n]_q$ is given by (1.4) and $z \in \mathbf{U}$.

Theorem 1 Let $\phi(z) = 1 + B_1 z + B_2 z^2 + \dots$ with $B_1 > 0$ and $B_2 \geq 0$. Let

$$\sigma_1 = \frac{([2]_q - \psi_2) B_1^2 \psi_2 + ([2]_q - \psi_2)^2 (B_2 - B_1)}{([3]_q - \psi_3) B_1^2}, \quad (2.1)$$

$$\sigma_2 = \frac{([2]_q - \psi_2) B_1^2 \psi_2 + ([2]_q - \psi_2)^2 (B_2 + B_1)}{([3]_q - \psi_3) B_1^2}. \quad (2.2)$$

If $f(z)$ given by (1.1) belongs to $\mathbf{S}_{j,k}^q(\phi)$, then

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq \begin{cases} \frac{B_2}{[3]_q - \psi_3} + \frac{B_1^2}{[2]_q - \psi_2} \left(\frac{\psi_2}{[3]_q - \psi_3} - \frac{\mu}{[2]_q - \psi_2} \right) & \text{if } \mu \leq \sigma_1, \\ \frac{B_1}{[3]_q - \psi_3} & \text{if } \sigma_1 \leq \mu \leq \sigma_2, \\ -\frac{B_2}{[3]_q - \psi_3} - \frac{B_1^2}{[2]_q - \psi_2} \left(\frac{\psi_2}{[3]_q - \psi_3} - \frac{\mu}{[2]_q - \psi_2} \right) & \text{if } \mu \geq \sigma_2. \end{cases} \quad (2.3)$$

where ψ_n is defined by (1.7). The result is sharp.

Proof. If $f \in \mathbf{S}_{j,k}^q(\phi)$, then there exists a Schwarz function $\omega(z)$, which is analytic in $\mathbf{U}$ with $w(0)=0$ and $|w(z)| < 1 \in \mathbf{U}$ such that

$$\frac{zD_q f(z)}{f_{j,k}(z)} = \phi(\omega(z)). \quad (2.4)$$

Define the function $p(z)$ by

$$p(z) = \frac{1 + \omega(z)}{1 - \omega(z)} = 1 + c_1 z + c_2 z^2 + \dots, z \in \mathbf{U}. \quad (2.5)$$

Since $\omega(z)$ is Schwarz function, we see that $\operatorname{Re} p(z) > 0$ and $p(z) = 1$.

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(\omega(z)) &= \phi\left(\frac{p(z) - 1}{p(z) + 1}\right) \\ &= \phi\left(\frac{1}{2} \left[c_1 z + \left(c_2 - \frac{c_1^2}{2} \right) z^2 + \left(c_3 - c_1 c_2 + \frac{c_1^3}{4} \right) z^3 + \dots \right] \right) \\ &= 1 + \frac{1}{2} B_1 c_1 z + \left[\frac{1}{2} B_1 \left(c_2 - \frac{c_1^2}{2} \right) + \frac{1}{4} B_2 c_1^2 \right] z^2 + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (2.6)$$

Now by substituting (2.6) in (2.4), we have

$$\frac{zD_q f(z)}{f_{j,k}(z)} = 1 + \frac{1}{2} B_1 c_1 z + \left[\frac{1}{2} B_1 \left(c_2 - \frac{c_1^2}{2} \right) + \frac{1}{4} B_2 c_1^2 \right] z^2 + \dots.$$

From this equation, we obtain

$$([2]_q - \psi_2) a_2 = \frac{B_1 c_1}{2}$$

$$([3]_q - \psi_3) a_3 - ([2]_q - \psi_2) \psi_2 a_2^2 = \frac{B_1 c_2}{2} - \frac{B_1 c_1^2}{4} + \frac{B_2 c_1^2}{4},$$

or equivalently

$$a_2 = \frac{B_1 c_1}{2([2]_q - \psi_2)}$$

$$a_3 = \frac{B_1}{2([3]_q - \psi_3)} \left(c_2 - \frac{c_1^2}{2} \left(1 - \frac{B_2}{B_1} - \frac{B_1 \psi_2}{[2]_q - \psi_2} \right) \right).$$

Therefore,

$$a_3 - \mu a_2^2 = \frac{B_1}{2([3]_q - \psi_3)} (c_2 - \nu c_1^2), \quad (2.7)$$

where

$$\nu = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 - \frac{B_2}{B_1} + \frac{B_1}{[2]_q - \psi_2} \left(\psi_2 - \frac{[3]_q - \psi_3}{[2]_q - \psi_2} \mu \right) \right]. \quad (2.8)$$

Our result now follows by an application of Lemma 2.

To show that the bounds are sharp, we define the functions K_{ϕ_n} ($n = 2, 3, 4, \dots$) by

$$\frac{z D_q K_{\phi_n}(z)}{K_{\phi_n}(z)} = \phi(z^{n-1}), \quad K_{\phi_n}(0) = 0 = K'_{\phi_n}(0) - 1$$

and the functions F_λ and G_λ ($0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$) by

$$\frac{z D_q F_\lambda(z)}{F_\lambda(z)} = \phi\left(\frac{z(z+\lambda)}{1+\lambda z}\right), \quad F_\lambda(0) = 0 = F'_\lambda(0) - 1$$

and

$$\frac{z D_q G_\lambda(z)}{G_\lambda(z)} = \phi\left(-\frac{1+\lambda z}{z(z+\lambda)}\right), \quad G_\lambda(0) = 0 = G'_\lambda(0) - 1.$$

Clearly, the functions K_{ϕ_n}, F_λ and $G_\lambda \in \mathbf{S}_{j,k}^q(\phi)$. If $\mu < \sigma_1$ or $\mu > \sigma_2$, then the equality holds if and only if f is K_{ϕ_2} , or one of its rotations. When $\sigma_1 < \mu < \sigma_2$, the equality holds if and only if f is K_{ϕ_3} , or one of its rotations. If $\mu = \sigma_1$, then the equality holds if and only if f is F_λ , or one of its rotations. If $\mu = \sigma_2$, then the equality holds if and only if f is G_λ , or one of its rotations.

Theorem 2 Let $\phi(z) = 1 + B_1 z + B_2 z^2 + \dots$ with $B_1 > 0$. Let $f(z)$ given by (1.1) belongs to $\mathbf{S}_{j,k}^q(\phi)$ and σ_3 given by

$$\sigma_3 = \frac{([2]_q - \psi_2) B_1^2 \psi_2 + ([2]_q - \psi_2)^2 B_2}{([3]_q - \psi_3) B_1^2}.$$

If $\sigma_1 \leq \mu \leq \sigma_3$, then

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| + \frac{([2]_q - \psi_2)^2}{([3]_q - \psi_3) B_1^2} \left[B_1 - B_2 - \frac{B_1^2}{[2]_q - \psi_2} \left(\psi_2 - \frac{[3]_q - \psi_3}{[2]_q - \psi_2} \mu \right) \right] |a_2|^2 \leq \frac{B_1}{[3]_q - \psi_3}.$$

If $\sigma_3 \leq \mu \leq \sigma_2$, then

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| + \frac{([2]_q - \psi_2)^2}{([3]_q - \psi_3) B_1^2} \left[B_1 + B_2 + \frac{B_1^2}{[2]_q - \psi_2} \left(\psi_2 - \frac{[3]_q - \psi_3}{[2]_q - \psi_2} \mu \right) \right] |a_2|^2 \leq \frac{B_1}{[3]_q - \psi_3},$$

where ψ_n is defined by (1.7). The result is sharp.

Remark 1

- For $q \rightarrow I^-$ in Theorem 1 and 2, we get the result similar to those obtained by Al Sarari and Latha in [4].
- For $q \rightarrow I^-, j = 1$ in Theorem 1 and 2, we get the result similar to those obtained by Al-Shaqsi and Darus in [5].
- For $q \rightarrow I^-, j = 1, k = 2$ in Theorem 1 and 2, we get the result similar to those obtained by Shanmugam et al. in [28].
- For $q \rightarrow I^-, j = 1, k = 1$ in Theorem 1 and 2, we get the result similar to those obtained by Ma and Minda in [19].

Theorem 3 Let $\phi(z) = 1 + B_1z + B_2z^2 + \dots (B_1 \neq 0)$. If $f(z) \in \mathbf{S}_{j,k}^q(\phi)$, then

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq \frac{|B_1|}{[3]_q - \psi_3} \max \left\{ 1; \left| \frac{B_2}{B_1} + \frac{B_1}{[2]_q - \psi_2} \left(\psi_2 - \frac{[3]_q - \psi_3}{[2]_q - \psi_2} \mu \right) \right| \right\}. \quad (2.9)$$

The result is sharp.

Taking $q \rightarrow I^-$ in Theorem 3, we obtain the following result for the functions belonging to the class $\mathbf{S}_{j,k}(\phi)$.

Corollary 1 [4] Let $\phi(z) = 1 + B_1z + B_2z^2 + \dots (B_1 \neq 0)$. If $f(z) \in \mathbf{S}_{j,k}(\phi)$, then

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq \frac{|B_1|}{3 - \psi_3} \max \left\{ 1; \left| \frac{B_2}{B_1} + \frac{B_1}{2 - \psi_2} \left(\psi_2 - \frac{3 - \psi_3}{2 - \psi_2} \mu \right) \right| \right\}.$$

The result is sharp.

Taking $q \rightarrow I^-$, $j = 1$ and $k = 1$ in Theorem 3, we obtain the following result for the functions belonging to the class $\mathbf{S}_{1,1}(\phi)$.

Corollary 2 Let $\phi(z) = 1 + B_1z + B_2z^2 + \dots (B_1 \neq 0)$. If $f(z) \in \mathbf{S}_{1,1}(\phi)$, then

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq \frac{|B_1|}{2} \max \left\{ 1; \left| \frac{B_2}{B_1} + B_1(1 - 2\mu) \right| \right\}.$$

The result is sharp.

Taking $q \rightarrow I^-$, $j = 1$ and $k = 2$ in Theorem 3, we obtain the following result for the functions belonging to the class $\mathbf{S}_{1,2}(\phi)$.

Corollary 3 Let $\phi(z) = 1 + B_1z + B_2z^2 + \dots (B_1 \neq 0)$. If $f(z) \in \mathbf{S}_{1,2}(\phi)$, then

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq \frac{|B_1|}{2} \max \left\{ 1; \left| \frac{B_2}{B_1} - \frac{B_1\mu}{2} \right| \right\}.$$

The result is sharp.

Theorem 4 Let $\phi(z) = 1 + B_1z + B_2z^2 + \dots$ with $B_1 > 0$. If $f(z)$ given by (1.1) belongs to $\mathbf{C}_{j,k}^q(\phi)$, then

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq \frac{|B_1|}{[3]_q([3]_q - \psi_3)} \max \left\{ 1; \left| \frac{B_2}{B_1} + \frac{B_1}{[2]_q - \psi_2} \left(\psi_2 - \frac{[3]_q([3]_q - \psi_3)}{([2]_q)^2([2]_q - \psi_2)} \mu \right) \right| \right\}. \quad (2.10)$$

The result is sharp.

Taking $q \rightarrow I^-$ in Theorem 4, we obtain the following result for the functions belonging to the class $\mathbf{C}_{j,k}(\phi)$.

Corollary 4 Let $\phi(z) = 1 + B_1z + B_2z^2 + \dots$ with $B_1 > 0$. If $f(z)$ given by (1.1) belongs to $\mathbf{C}_{j,k}(\phi)$, then

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq \frac{|B_1|}{3(3 - \psi_3)} \max \left\{ 1; \left| \frac{B_2}{B_1} + \frac{B_1}{2 - \psi_2} \left(\psi_2 - \frac{3(3 - \psi_3)}{2^2(2 - \psi_2)} \mu \right) \right| \right\}.$$

The result is sharp.

Taking $q \rightarrow I^-$, $j = 1$ and $k = 1$ in Theorem 4, we obtain the following result for the functions belonging to the class $\mathbf{C}_{1,1}(\phi)$.

Corollary 5 Let $\phi(z) = 1 + B_1z + B_2z^2 + \dots$ with $B_1 > 0$. If $f(z)$ given by (1.1) belongs to $\mathbf{C}_{1,1}(\phi)$, then

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq \frac{|B_1|}{6} \max \left\{ 1; \left| \frac{B_2}{B_1} + B_1 \left(1 - \frac{3\mu}{2} \right) \right| \right\}.$$

The result is sharp.

Taking $q \rightarrow I^-$, $j = 1$ and $k = 2$ in Theorem 4, we obtain the following result for the functions belonging to the

class $C_{1,2}(\phi)$.

Corollary 6 Let $\phi(z) = 1 + B_1z + B_2z^2 + \dots$ with $B_1 > 0$. If $f(z)$ given by (1.1) belongs to $C_{1,2}(\phi)$, then

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq \frac{|B_1|}{6} \max \left\{ 1, \left| \frac{B_2}{B_1} - \frac{3B_1\mu}{8} \right| \right\}.$$

The result is sharp.

Theorem 5 Let $\phi(z) = 1 + B_1z + B_2z^2 + \dots$ with $B_1 > 0$ and $B_2 \geq 0$. Let

$$\chi_1 = \frac{([2]_q)^2 ([2]_q - \psi_2) [B_1^2 \psi_2 + ([2]_q - \psi_2) (B_2 - B_1)]}{B_1^2 [3]_q ([3]_q - \psi_3)},$$

$$\chi_2 = \frac{([2]_q)^2 ([2]_q - \psi_2) [B_1^2 \psi_2 + ([2]_q - \psi_2) (B_2 + B_1)]}{B_1^2 [3]_q ([3]_q - \psi_3)},$$

$$\chi_3 = \frac{([2]_q)^2 ([2]_q - \psi_2) [B_1^2 \psi_2 + ([2]_q - \psi_2) B_2]}{B_1^2 [3]_q ([3]_q - \psi_3)}.$$

If $f(z)$ given by (1.1) belongs to $C_{j,k}^q(\phi)$ with $b > 0$, then

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq \begin{cases} \frac{B_2}{[3]_q([3]_q - \psi_3)} + \frac{B_1^2}{[3]_q([3]_q - \psi_3)([2]_q - \psi_2)} \left(\psi_2 - \frac{[3]_q([3]_q - \psi_3)}{([2]_q)^2([2]_q - \psi_2)} \mu \right) & \text{if } \mu \leq \chi_1, \\ \frac{B_1}{[3]_q([3]_q - \psi_3)} & \text{if } \chi_1 \leq \mu \leq \chi_2, \\ -\frac{B_2}{[3]_q([3]_q - \psi_3)} - \frac{B_1^2}{[3]_q([3]_q - \psi_3)([2]_q - \psi_2)} \left(\psi_2 - \frac{[3]_q([3]_q - \psi_3)}{([2]_q)^2([2]_q - \psi_2)} \mu \right) & \text{if } \mu \geq \chi_2. \end{cases} \quad (2.11)$$

Further, if $\chi_1 \leq \mu \leq \chi_3$, then

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| + \frac{([2]_q)^2 ([2]_q - \psi_2)^2}{[3]_q([3]_q - \psi_3) B_1^2} \left[B_1 - B_2 - \frac{B_1^2}{[2]_q - \psi_2} \left(\psi_2 - \frac{[3]_q([3]_q - \psi_3)}{([2]_q)^2([2]_q - \psi_2)} \mu \right) \right] |a_2|^2$$

$$\leq \frac{B_1}{[3]_q([3]_q - \psi_3)}.$$

If $\chi_3 \leq \mu \leq \chi_2$, then

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| + \frac{([2]_q)^2 ([2]_q - \psi_2)^2}{[3]_q([3]_q - \psi_3) B_1^2} \left[B_1 + B_2 + \frac{B_1^2}{[2]_q - \psi_2} \left(\psi_2 - \frac{[3]_q([3]_q - \psi_3)}{([2]_q)^2([2]_q - \psi_2)} \mu \right) \right] |a_2|^2$$

$$\leq \frac{B_1}{[3]_q([3]_q - \psi_3)}.$$

The result is sharp.

Taking $q \rightarrow 1^-$ in Theorem 5, we obtain the following result for the functions belonging to the class $C_{j,k}(\phi)$.

Corollary 7 Let $\phi(z) = 1 + B_1z + B_2z^2 + \dots$ with $B_1 > 0$ and $B_2 \geq 0$. Let

$$\chi_1 = \frac{(2)^2 (2 - \psi_2) [B_1^2 \psi_2 + (2 - \psi_2) (B_2 - B_1)]}{B_1^2 3(3 - \psi_3)},$$

$$\chi_2 = \frac{(2)^2(2-\psi_2)[B_1^2\psi_2 + (2-\psi_2)(B_2 + B_1)]}{B_1^2 3(3-\psi_3)},$$

$$\chi_3 = \frac{(2)^2(2-\psi_2)[B_1^2\psi_2 + (2-\psi_2)B_2]}{B_1^2 3(3-\psi_3)}.$$

If $f(z)$ given by (1.1) belongs to $\mathbf{C}_{j,k}(\phi)$ with $b > 0$, then

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq \begin{cases} \frac{B_2}{3(3-\psi_3)} + \frac{B_1^2}{3(3-\psi_3)(2-\psi_2)} \left(\psi_2 - \frac{3(3-\psi_3)}{(2)^2(2-\psi_2)} \mu \right) & \text{if } \mu \leq \chi_1, \\ \frac{B_1}{3(3-\psi_3)} & \text{if } \chi_1 \leq \mu \leq \chi_2, \\ -\frac{B_2}{3(3-\psi_3)} - \frac{B_1^2}{3(3-\psi_3)(2-\psi_2)} \left(\psi_2 - \frac{3(3-\psi_3)}{(2)^2(2-\psi_2)} \mu \right) & \text{if } \mu \geq \chi_2. \end{cases}$$

Further, if $\chi_1 \leq \mu \leq \chi_3$, then

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| + \frac{(2)^2(2-\psi_2)^2}{3(3-\psi_3)B_1^2} \left[B_1 - B_2 - \frac{B_1^2}{2-\psi_2} \left(\psi_2 - \frac{3(3-\psi_3)}{(2)^2(2-\psi_2)} \mu \right) \right] |a_2|^2 \leq \frac{B_1}{3(3-\psi_3)}.$$

If $\chi_3 \leq \mu \leq \chi_2$, then

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| + \frac{(2)^2(2-\psi_2)^2}{3(3-\psi_3)B_1^2} \left[B_1 + B_2 + \frac{B_1^2}{2-\psi_2} \left(\psi_2 - \frac{3(3-\psi_3)}{(2)^2(2-\psi_2)} \mu \right) \right] |a_2|^2 \leq \frac{B_1}{3(3-\psi_3)}.$$

The result is sharp.

Remark 2

- For $q \rightarrow I^-$, $j = 1, k = 1$ in Theorem 5, we get the result similar to those obtained by Ma and Minda in [19].
- For $q \rightarrow I^-$, $j = 1, k = 2$ in Theorem 5, we get the result similar to those obtained by Shanmugam et al. in [28].

3. Applications to Functions Defined by Fractional Derivatives:

In order to introduce classes $\mathbf{S}_{j,k}^{q,\lambda}(\phi)$ and $\mathbf{C}_{j,k}^{q,\lambda}(\phi)$ we need the following.

Definition 3.1 Let $f(z)$ be analytic in a simply connected region of the Z -plane containing the origin. The fractional derivative of f of order λ is defined by

$$D_z^\lambda f(z) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\lambda)} \frac{d}{dz} \int_0^z \frac{f(\zeta)}{(z-\zeta)^\lambda} d\zeta, \quad (0 \leq \lambda < 1) \quad (3.1)$$

where the multiplicity of $(z-\zeta)^{-\lambda}$ is removed by requiring that $\log(z-\zeta)$ to be real for $z-\zeta > 0$.

Using the definition 3.1 and its known extensions involving fractional derivatives and fractional integrals, Owa and Srivastava [22] introduced the operator $\Omega^\lambda : \mathbf{A} \rightarrow \mathbf{A}$ defined by

$$(\Omega^\lambda f)(z) = \Gamma(2-\lambda) z^\lambda D_z^\lambda f(z), \quad (\lambda \neq 2, 3, 4, \dots). \quad (3.2)$$

Classes $\mathbf{S}_{j,k}^{q,\lambda}(\phi)$ and $\mathbf{C}_{j,k}^{q,\lambda}(\phi)$ consist of functions $f \in \mathbf{A}$ for which $\Omega^\lambda f \in \mathbf{S}_{j,k}^q(\phi)$ and $\Omega^\lambda f \in \mathbf{C}_{j,k}^q(\phi)$, respectively.

For a fixed $g \in \mathbf{A}$, let $\mathbf{S}_{j,k}^{q,g}(\phi)$ be the class of functions $f \in \mathbf{A}$ for which $(f * g) \in \mathbf{S}_{j,k}^q(\phi)$ and let $\mathbf{C}_{j,k}^{q,g}(\phi)$ be the class of functions $f \in \mathbf{A}$ for which $(f * g) \in \mathbf{C}_{j,k}^q(\phi)$.

Classes $\mathbf{S}_{j,k}^{q,\lambda}(\phi)$ and $\mathbf{C}_{j,k}^{q,\lambda}(\phi)$ are the special case of classes $\mathbf{S}_{j,k}^{q,g}(\phi)$ and $\mathbf{C}_{j,k}^{q,g}(\phi)$, respectively, when

$$g(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(n+1)\Gamma(2-\lambda)}{\Gamma(n+1-\lambda)} a_n z^n. \quad (3.3)$$

Let

$$g(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} g_n z^n \quad (g_n > 0),$$

$$f(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n z^n. \quad (3.4)$$

Since $f \in \mathbf{S}_{j,k}^{q,s}(\phi) (\mathbf{C}_{j,k}^{q,s}(\phi))$ if and only if $f * g \in \mathbf{S}_{j,k}^q(\phi) (\mathbf{C}_{j,k}^q(\phi))$, we obtain the coefficient estimates for functions in classes $\mathbf{S}_{j,k}^{q,s}(\phi)$ and $\mathbf{C}_{j,k}^{q,s}(\phi)$, from the corresponding estimates for functions in classes $\mathbf{S}_{j,k}^q(\phi)$ and $\mathbf{C}_{j,k}^q(\phi)$.

Applying Theorem 1 for the function $(f * g)(z) = z + g_2 a_2 z^2 + g_3 a_3 z^3 + \dots$, we get the following theorem for an obvious change of μ .

Theorem 6 Let the function $\phi(z) = 1 + B_1 z + B_2 z^2 + \dots$ and let $g(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} g_n z^n$ ($g_n > 0$). If $f(z)$ given

by(1.3) belongs to $\mathbf{S}_{j,k}^{q,s}(\phi)$, then

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq \begin{cases} \frac{1}{g_3([3]_q - \psi_3)} \left[B_2 + \frac{B_1^2 \psi_2}{[2]_q - \psi_2} - \mu \frac{g_3}{g_2^2} \frac{B_1^2 ([3]_q - \psi_3)}{([2]_q - \psi_2)^2} \right], & \text{if } \mu \leq \tau_1; \\ \frac{B_1}{g_3([3]_q - \psi_3)}, & \text{if } \tau_1 \leq \mu \leq \tau_2; \text{ where} \\ -\frac{1}{g_3([3]_q - \psi_3)} \left[B_2 + \frac{B_1^2 \psi_2}{[2]_q - \psi_2} - \mu \frac{g_3}{g_2^2} \frac{B_1^2 ([3]_q - \psi_3)}{([2]_q - \psi_2)^2} \right], & \text{if } \mu \geq \tau_2. \end{cases}$$

$$\tau_1 = \frac{g_2^2 ([2]_q - \psi_2)^2}{g_3 B_1 ([3]_q - \psi_3)} \left[-1 + \frac{B_2}{B_1} + \frac{B_1 \psi_2}{([2]_q - \psi_2)} \right],$$

and

$$\tau_2 = \frac{g_2^2 ([2]_q - \psi_2)^2}{g_3 B_1 ([3]_q - \psi_3)} \left[1 + \frac{B_2}{B_1} + \frac{B_1 \psi_2}{([2]_q - \psi_2)} \right],$$

where ψ_n is defined by (1.7). The result is sharp.

Remark 3 Since $\Omega^\lambda f(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(n+1)\Gamma(2-\lambda)}{\Gamma(n+1-\lambda)} a_n z^n$,

we have

$$g_2 = \frac{\Gamma(3)\Gamma(2-\lambda)}{\Gamma(3-\lambda)} = \frac{2}{2-\lambda}, \quad (3.5)$$

$$g_3 = \frac{\Gamma(4)\Gamma(2-\lambda)}{\Gamma(4-\lambda)} = \frac{6}{(2-\lambda)(3-\lambda)}. \quad (3.6)$$

For g_2, g_3 given by (3.5) and (3.6) respectively, Theorem 6 reduces to the following Corollary.

Corollary 8 Let $\lambda < 2$. If $f(z)$ given by(1.3) belongs to $\mathbf{S}_{j,k}^{q,\lambda}(\phi)$, then

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq \begin{cases} \frac{(2-\lambda)(3-\lambda)}{6([3]_q - \psi_3)} \left[B_2 + \frac{B_1^2 \psi_2}{[2]_q - \psi_2} - \mu \frac{3(2-\lambda)}{2(3-\lambda)} \frac{B_1^2 ([3]_q - \psi_3)}{([2]_q - \psi_2)^2} \right], & \text{if } \mu \leq \tau_1^*; \\ \frac{(2-\lambda)(3-\lambda) B_1}{6([3]_q - \psi_3)}, & \text{if } \tau_1^* \leq \mu \leq \tau_2^*; \\ -\frac{(2-\lambda)(3-\lambda)}{6([3]_q - \psi_3)} \left[B_2 + \frac{B_1^2 \psi_2}{[2]_q - \psi_2} - \mu \frac{3(2-\lambda)}{2(3-\lambda)} \frac{B_1^2 ([3]_q - \psi_3)}{([2]_q - \psi_2)^2} \right], & \text{if } \mu \geq \tau_2^*. \end{cases}$$

where

$$\tau_1^* = \frac{2(3-\lambda)}{3(2-\lambda)} \frac{([2]_q - \psi_2)^2}{B_1([3]_q - \psi_3)} \left[-1 + \frac{B_2}{B_1} + \frac{B_1 \psi_2}{([2]_q - \psi_2)} \right],$$

and

$$\tau_2^* = \frac{2(3-\lambda)}{3(2-\lambda)} \frac{([2]_q - \psi_2)^2}{B_1([3]_q - \psi_3)} \left[1 + \frac{B_2}{B_1} + \frac{B_1 \psi_2}{([2]_q - \psi_2)} \right],$$

where ψ_n is defined by (1.7). The result is sharp.

Remark 4

- For $q \rightarrow I^-$ in Theorem 6 and Corollary 8, we get the result similar to those obtained by Al Sarari and Latha in [4].
- For $q \rightarrow I^-, j = 1$ in Theorem 6, we get the result similar to those obtained by Al-Shaqsi and Darus in [5].
- For $q \rightarrow I^-, j = 1, k = 2$ in Theorem 6, we get the result similar to those obtained by Shanmugam et al. in [28].

Theorem 7 Let the function $\phi(z) = 1 + B_1 z + B_2 z^2 + \dots$ and let $g(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} g_n z^n$ ($g_n > 0$). If $f(z)$ given

by(1.3) belongs to $\mathbf{C}_{j,k}^{q,g}(\phi)$, then

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq \begin{cases} \frac{1}{g_3 [3]_q ([3]_q - \psi_3)} \left[B_2 + \frac{B_1^2 \psi_2}{[2]_q - \psi_2} - \mu \frac{g_3}{g_2^2} \frac{B_1^2 [3]_q ([3]_q - \psi_3)}{[2]_q^2 ([2]_q - \psi_2)^2} \right], & \text{if } \mu \leq \tau_1; \\ \frac{B_1}{g_3 [3]_q ([3]_q - \psi_3)}, & \text{if } \tau_1 \leq \mu \leq \tau_2; \\ -\frac{1}{g_3 [3]_q ([3]_q - \psi_3)} \left[B_2 + \frac{B_1^2 \psi_2}{[2]_q - \psi_2} - \mu \frac{g_3}{g_2^2} \frac{B_1^2 [3]_q ([3]_q - \psi_3)}{[2]_q^2 ([2]_q - \psi_2)^2} \right], & \text{if } \mu \geq \tau_2. \end{cases}$$

where

$$\tau_1 = \frac{g_2^2 [2]_q^2 ([2]_q - \psi_2)^2}{g_3 B_1 [3]_q ([3]_q - \psi_3)} \left[-1 + \frac{B_2}{B_1} + \frac{B_1 \psi_2}{([2]_q - \psi_2)} \right],$$

and

$$\tau_2 = \frac{g_2^2 [2]_q^2 ([2]_q - \psi_2)^2}{g_3 B_1 [3]_q ([3]_q - \psi_3)} \left[1 + \frac{B_2}{B_1} + \frac{B_1 \psi_2}{([2]_q - \psi_2)} \right],$$

where ψ_n is defined by (1.7). The result is sharp.

For g_2, g_3 given by (3.5) and (3.6) respectively, Theorem 7 reduces to the following Corollary.

Corollary 9 Let $\lambda < 2$. If $f(z)$ given by(1.3) belongs to $\mathbf{C}_{j,k}^{q,\lambda}(\phi)$, then

$$|a_3 - \mu a_2^2| \leq \begin{cases} \frac{(2-\lambda)(3-\lambda)}{6[3]_q([3]_q - \psi_3)} \left[B_2 + \frac{B_1^2 \psi_2}{[2]_q - \psi_2} - \mu \frac{3(2-\lambda)}{2(3-\lambda)} \frac{B_1^2 [3]_q ([3]_q - \psi_3)}{[2]_q^2 ([2]_q - \psi_2)^2} \right], & \text{if } \mu \leq \tau_1^*; \\ \frac{(2-\lambda)(3-\lambda) B_1}{6[3]_q ([3]_q - \psi_3)}, & \text{if } \tau_1^* \leq \mu \leq \tau_2^*; \\ -\frac{(2-\lambda)(3-\lambda)}{6[3]_q ([3]_q - \psi_3)} \left[B_2 + \frac{B_1^2 \psi_2}{[2]_q - \psi_2} - \mu \frac{3(2-\lambda)}{2(3-\lambda)} \frac{B_1^2 [3]_q ([3]_q - \psi_3)}{[2]_q^2 ([2]_q - \psi_2)^2} \right], & \text{if } \mu \geq \tau_2^*. \end{cases}$$

where

$$\tau_1^* = \frac{2(3-\lambda)}{3(2-\lambda)} \frac{[2]_q^2 ([2]_q - \psi_2)^2}{B_1 [3]_q ([3]_q - \psi_3)} \left[-1 + \frac{B_2}{B_1} + \frac{B_1 \psi_2}{([2]_q - \psi_2)} \right],$$

and

$$\tau_2^* = \frac{2(3-\lambda)}{3(2-\lambda)} \frac{[2]_q^2 ([2]_q - \psi_2)^2}{B_1 [3]_q ([3]_q - \psi_3)} \left[1 + \frac{B_2}{B_1} + \frac{B_1 \psi_2}{([2]_q - \psi_2)} \right],$$

where ψ_n is defined by (1.7). The result is sharp.

Remark 5:

For $q \rightarrow 1^-$, $j = 1, k = 2$ in Theorem 7 and Corollary 9, we get the result similar to those obtained by Shanmugam et al. in [28].

References:

1. R. P. Agarwal, Certain fractional q -integrals and q -derivatives, Proc. Cambridge Philos. Soc. 66 (1969), 365–370.
2. H. Aldweby and M. Darus, A subclass of harmonic univalent functions associated with q -analogue of Dziok-Srivastava operator, ISRN Math. Anal. Vol. 2013, Art. ID 382312, 1–6.
3. W. A. Al-Salam, Some fractional q -integrals and q -derivatives, Proc. Edinburgh Math. Soc. (2) 15 (1966/1967), 135–140.
4. F. S. M. Al Sarari and S. Latha, Fekete-Szegő inequalities and (j, k) -symmetric functions, Electron. J. Math. Anal. Appl. 3 (2015), no. 2, 249–256.
5. K. Al-Shaqsi and M. Darus, Fekete-Szegő problem for univalent functions with respect to k -symmetric points, Aust. J. Math. Anal. Appl. 5(2), (2008), 1-12.
6. M. K. Aouf, F. M. Al-Oboudi and M. M. Haidan, On some results for λ -spirallike and λ -Robertson functions of complex order, Publ. Inst. Math. (Beograd) (N.S.) 77(91) (2005), 93–98.
7. A. Aral and V. Gupta, Generalized q -Baskakov operators, Math. Slovaca 61 (2011), no. 4, 619–634.
8. A. Aral, V. Gupta and R. P. Agarwal, Applications of q -calculus in operator theory, Springer, New York, 2013.
9. T. Bulboacă, Differential Subordinations and Superordinations, Recent Results, House of Scientific Book Publ., Cluj-Napoca, 2005.
10. P. L. Duren, Univalent functions, Springer, New York, 1983.
11. B. A. Frasin, Family of analytic functions of complex order, Acta Math. Acad. Paedagog. Nyházi. (N.S.) 22 (2006), no. 2, 179–191.
12. A. W. Goodman, Univalent functions. Vol. I, II, Mariner, Tampa, FL, 1983.
13. A. W. Goodman, On uniformly convex functions, Ann. Polon. Math. 56 (1991), no. 1, 87–92.
14. A. W. Goodman, On uniformly starlike functions, J. Math. Anal. Appl. 155 (1991), no. 2, 364–370.
15. F. H. Jackson, On q -definite integrals, Quarterly J. Pure Appl. Math., 41 (1910), 193–203.
16. F. H. Jackson, On q -functions and a certain difference operator, Transactions of the Royal Society of Edinburgh, 46 (1908), 253–281.
17. V. Kac and P. Cheung, Quantum calculus, Universitext, Springer-Verlag, New York, 2002.
18. P. Liczberski and J. Polubinski, On (j, k) -symmetrical functions, Mathematica Bohemica, 120, (1995), 13-25.
19. W. C. Ma and D. Minda, A unified treatment of some special classes of univalent functions, in Proceedings of the Conference on Complex Analysis (Tianjin, 1992), 157–169, Conf. Proc. Lecture Notes Anal., I, Int. Press, Cambridge, MA.
20. S. S. Miller and P. T. Mocanu, Differential subordinations, Monographs and Textbooks in Pure and Applied Mathematics, Vol. 225, Dekker, New York, 2000.
21. A. Mohammed and M. Darus, A generalized operator involving the q -hypergeometric function, Mat. Vesnik 65

- (2013), no. 4, 454–465.
22. S. Owa and H. M. Srivastava, Univalent and starlike generalized hypergeometric functions, *Canad. J. Math.* 39 (1987), no. 5, 1057–1077.
 23. S. D. Purohit and R. K. Raina, Certain subclasses of analytic functions associated with fractional q -calculus operators, *Math. Scand.* 109 (2011), no. 1, 55–70.
 24. S. D. Purohit and R. K. Raina, Fractional q -calculus and certain subclasses of univalent analytic functions, *Mathematica* 55(78) (2013), no. 1, 62–74.
 25. C. Ramachandran, D. Kavitha and T. Soupramanien, Certain bound for q -starlike and q -convex functions with respect to symmetric points, *Int. J. Math. Math. Sci.* 2015, Art. ID 205682, 7 pp.
 26. V. Ravichandran et al., Certain subclasses of starlike and convex functions of complex order, *Hacet. J. Math. Stat.* 34 (2005), 9–15.
 27. A. C. Schaeffer and D. C. Spencer, Coefficient Regions for Schlicht Functions, American Mathematical Society Colloquium Publications, Vol. 35, Amer. Math. Soc., New York, NY, 1950.
 28. T. N. Shanmugam, C. Ramachandran and V. Ravichandran, Fekete-Szegő problem for subclasses of starlike functions with respect to symmetric points, *Bull. Korean Math. Soc.* 43 (2006), no. 3, 589–598.